

Emotion Management

Is The Key To Personal And Business Success

Assoc.Prof Yeşim SIRAKAYA¹

Reyhan DURUSU²

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¹ St Clements University ,Department of Psychology Orcid ID: 0009-0004-2558-8194, Mail:
yesimsirakaya8282@gmail.com

² St Clements University Social Psychology PhD, Orcid ID:0009-0002-9100-4797, Mail:
reyhandurusu@gmail.com

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Abstract

Although emotion, which is generally defined as intense feelings directed towards someone or something (Çakar and Arbak, 2004), gained importance especially in the 1980s, it is possible to say in the literature review that there are not enough studies on emotion and emotion management in our country. The concept of emotional intelligence has mostly been the subject of research by combining it with other variables. The purpose of this study is to emphasize the importance of emotion management by explaining the concept of emotion management and revealing its impact on the work-life balance of today's employees.

Keywords: Emotion, emotional management, work-life balance

Introduction

Individuals experience a variety of emotions both in their professional and personal lives, and emotions, as an integral part of human behavior, play a determining role in numerous areas,

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ranging from a person's inner world to interpersonal relationships. For this reason, emotions are said to hold a fundamental role in human behavior (Erkuş & Günlü, 2008). Emotions provide a foundation for individuals to prioritize their activities and decisions, assisting in their survival and influencing various actions and behaviors, which in turn shape their future (Kervancı, 2008). An individual cannot separate themselves from their emotions; however, through the development of skills and methods, they can manage their emotions and utilize them to serve their intended purpose.

Emotions are crucial for individuals as they can influence their outlook on life, morale, and performance in both negative and positive ways. If emotions are well-managed, they can positively affect an individual's morale and performance (Akın, 2004; Kervancı, 2008). Although research in the workplace has long been dominated by rational studies, it is evident that, particularly in recent years, the rational model has been increasingly questioned, and the concept of emotion in the workplace has gained more attention in the literature and research (Ashkanasy et al. 2002; Fineman, 2000; Payne & Cooper, 2001). The presence of emotions is especially pronounced in work environments where the human element is at the forefront. Given that emotions significantly influence behaviors, they are an essential factor to consider in understanding behaviors in the workplace.

Emotions

The concept of emotion has been examined through various disciplines such as biology, psychoanalysis, cognitive and social psychology, neurology, behavioral sciences, and economics, with different aspects of this concept being addressed (Küpers & Weibler, 2008). The existence of these diverse aspects has led to the absence of a universally accepted definition (Marcus, 2000). When we examine the definitions encountered, emotion is described as an impression and thought (feeling, sense) obtained through the senses (Demiray, 1988), and in the Oxford English Dictionary, emotion is defined as any agitation or movement of the mind, feeling, passion, or any intense or aroused mental state.

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Another definition describes emotion as a response involving physiological arousal, expressive behaviors, and conscious experiences, encompassing the organism as a whole (Myers & Dewall, 2017). From the perspective of neurologists, we see that they approach emotion within their field and reveal the neural pathways related to emotion (Ochner et al., 2009).

Our emotional responses follow two different brain pathways: some complex emotions, like hatred and love, follow the high road, passing through the thalamus to reach the brain cortex. In the cortex, emotions are examined and labeled before a response command is received via the amygdala, the emotion control center. However, sometimes our emotions follow a neural shortcut, bypassing the cortex, referred to by Joseph LeDoux as the low road. Examples of emotions following this low road include basic feelings such as liking or disliking something or situations, and fears (LeDoux, 1996).

The concept of emotion has been taken into consideration by many disciplines such as biology, psychoanalysis, cognitive and social psychology, neurology, behavioral sciences, and economics, and as a result, its many different dimensions have been explored (Küpers & Weibler, 2008). These diverse aspects contribute to the lack of a universally accepted definition (Marcus, 2000). Nevertheless, it is possible to describe emotions in their most general sense as direct responses that people exhibit toward different experiences and attitudes within a broad framework (Callahan & McCollum, 2002; Lazarus, 1999; Frijda, 1988).

In the discipline of psychology, various views have been utilized to theorize the concept of emotion, including terms such as "passion," "pleasure," "sentiment" (Dixon, 2012, p. 340), "desire," "sense," "affect" (Frevert, 2014, p. 52), or "accidents of the soul," "moral sentiments" (Watt Smith, 2018).

Generally, emotions are defined in terms of cognitive aspects for their intellectual features, biological components for their relation to the body, and behavioral aspects when considering the transformation of emotions into actions (Langelier, 2006).

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When we look at the basic clusters of emotions identified by researchers, we can outline the following core emotions:

- **Anger:** rage, insult, resentment, wrath, exhaustion, irritation, frustration, grudge, hostility, and even pathological hatred and violence
- **Sadness:** pain, grief, melancholy, gloom, self-pity, boredom, loneliness, hopelessness, and when pathological, severe depression
- **Fear:** anxiety, nervousness, worry, apprehension, suspicion, astonishment, alertness, unease, remorse, hesitation, terror, dread, and when pathological, phobia and panic
- **Pleasure:** happiness, enthusiasm, relaxation, satisfaction, joy, delight, sensual pleasure, excitement, ecstasy, rapture, whimsy, and at the highest level, mania
- **Love:** acceptance, trust, friendship, kindness, affection, loyalty, intense passion, admiration
- **Surprise:** shock, astonishment, curiosity, amazement
- **Disgust:** contempt, disdain, revulsion, hatred, repulsion, scorn
- **Shame:** guilt, disappointment, regret, distress, humiliation, remorse these core emotions can be listed as such (Goleman, 2019).

Emotion Management

The concept of emotion management is explained as the individual's ability to control their internal state and externally reflect the expected or desired emotion in order to display a response considered appropriate for the situation (Hochschild, 1979).

While individuals manage their emotions in different ways, social interactions in the workplace are significant areas that reveal the presence of the emotion management process and offer an opportunity for easy observation (Sloan, 2007).

The concept of emotion management is further elaborated by Çeşitçioğlu as “taking necessary measures to prevent emotional intelligence from taking control, keeping the brain

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under the management of rational thought, making a conscious effort to recognize emotions and deal with them effectively, neutralizing previously suppressed emotions in the subconscious, and ultimately gaining the ability to live in the moment” (Çeşitçioğlu, 2003).

Goleman (2004) emphasizes that emotion management does not imply that individuals or managers suppress their emotions or completely submit to their influence when forming opinions, making decisions, or expressing ideas. Instead, he underlines that facing emotions can lead individuals to successful outcomes (Töremen & Çankaya, 2008).

The ability to manage emotions significantly impacts both negative emotions such as low self-esteem, stress, anger, and anxiety, as well as positive emotions like joy, love, pleasure, and patience. Knowing how to recognize and control these emotions plays a crucial role in how individuals manage them (Kervancı, 2008).

Subfields of Emotion Management

The subfields of emotion management include self-regulation, self-awareness, communication, social skills, and empathy (Yaylacı, 2006). To briefly address these classifications.

1. Self-Regulation: Self-regulation is explained as the ability to control destructive emotions and the causes that lead to destruction. It is observed that individuals with the ability to regulate can manage their instincts and emotions that may cause harm to themselves (Goleman, 2000, p. 107). Cüceloğlu emphasizes that one of the primary purposes of self-regulation is to minimize potential problems in life by allowing individuals to control themselves in challenging situations and emotionally intense conditions, offering significant opportunities to the individual (Cüceloğlu, 1998).

2. Self-Awareness: Self-awareness refers to the recognition of one's emotional states. A self-aware person is not only conscious of what is happening within their inner world but also

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aware of how and to what extent others around them affect them (Cüceloğlu, 2005). In other words, self-awareness involves understanding the emotions one experiences, their effects, processes, alternatives, sources, and feelings (Avcı, 2014).

3. Communication: People communicate with others through their emotions. Individuals who can communicate effectively understand that relationships may fluctuate between positive and negative states and are better equipped to handle challenges, solve problems more easily, and register emotional data (Yan, 2008). In short, communication is ever-present in our lives, and just as eating is essential for survival, communication is equally important (Kervancı, 2008).

4. Social Skills: A more detailed definition of social skills includes influence, which refers to the ability to use effective persuasion methods; communication, which involves listening clearly and sending realistic messages; conflict management, which encompasses finding resolutions and compromises in disagreements; leadership, which includes guiding, advising, and leading individuals or groups; catalyzing and managing change; building relationships aimed at achieving specific goals; cooperating with others for common objectives; and team skills, which involve fostering group synergy while observing collective goals (Goleman, 2011).

5. Empathy: Empathy is defined as "the process of projecting oneself into another object, feeling as though one is inside that object, and thereby understanding it by internalizing/absorbing it" (Ersoy & Köşger, 2016). Another definition describes empathy as the perspective formed by understanding the emotions and thoughts of the person one is communicating with (Dökmen, 2009). A key aspect of empathy is the necessity of active listening skills to communicate with and understand the other person (Kervancı, 2008). However, in empathy, the goal is not to agree with or accept everything the other person says, but to understand them. This facilitates not only empathic communication but also lays the groundwork for healthy communication (Baltaş, 2006, p. 24).

Emotions and Emotion Management in the Workplace:

Emotions not only inform individuals about external events but also influence their personal goals (Özkalp & Cengiz, 2003; Yelkikalan, 2006). Emotions, which form the basis of behavior, prompt individuals to act and guide their actions. The key functions of emotions are outlined in three main points: preparing individuals for action, shaping future behaviors, and helping regulate social relationships (Çakar, 2002; Acar, 2007).

In the context of the workplace, it is expected that individuals understand their emotions and mobilize their goals in line with organizational guidance. It is essential for employees to establish social relationships with their colleagues and to effectively use their empathy skills. In this regard, it is critical that employees effectively utilize their emotional competencies in the workplace (Titrek, 2007). Individuals encounter many emotions both in their professional and personal lives. This is a fundamental aspect of human behavior, influencing various areas from one's inner world to interpersonal relationships, and playing a crucial role in shaping human behavior (Erkuş & Günlü, 2008).

It is evident that various emotions are experienced in the workplace (Rafaeli & Worline, 2001). In contemporary societies, workplaces are among the most emotionally charged environments where individuals exist (Seçer, 2007). When emotions are well-managed, they can enhance both morale and performance (Akin, 2004; Kervancı, 2008).

Emotional management is seen today as an important source of social capital and synergy in intra-organizational relations (Töremen and Çankaya, 2008). In a comprehensive study by George and Brief (1996) that explored the connections between job motivation and emotions, it was found that employees who experience positive emotions in their organizations tend to interpret work-related events from a positive perspective and adopt a more optimistic outlook regarding the likelihood of future success (Özçelik et al. 2008).

Research indicates that emotion management practices positively affect both organizational and individual performance, highlighting the importance of emotion

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management (Özçelik et al. 2008). Studies have shown that positive emotion management significantly contributes to the healthy operational integrity of organizations from individual, organizational, and managerial perspectives. By influencing employee job satisfaction and contentment levels, it also positively impacts job performance. Based on this information, it is reasonable to assert that positive emotion management will yield favorable outcomes for organizations and management (Özçelik et al. 2008).

When considering employee job satisfaction, emotion management is a crucial factor. Positive emotion management allows employees to derive greater satisfaction from their work, while negative emotion management can adversely affect job satisfaction. Therefore, the development of emotion management skills in the workplace will positively influence success at both individual and organizational levels (Brotheridge, 2003).

Work-Life Balance

Work-life balance is explained as a strategic human resource management tool designed to enable employees to balance their roles and responsibilities between work and family, while also ensuring their well-being (Apaydın, 2011; Koray, 2016; Özdevecioğlu & Çakmak Doruk, 2009). The concept of work-life balance has been noted to encompass various interconnected areas similar to links in a chain, such as "family life," "work life," "educational life," and an individual's social activities (Uslu, 2020). It is possible to categorize an individual's non-work life under "private life," which includes not only time spent with family but also time dedicated to oneself and hobbies, time spent with relatives, friends, and acquaintances, as well as time for matters related to home, health, and other responsibilities (Keser & Kümbül Güler, 2016).

Objective

According to the results of a study conducted by the Gallup organization at the United Nations in 2024, based on 143 countries to measure the stress, happiness, and anger levels of citizens, Turkey ranked third globally in terms of anger, stress, and sadness. In contrast, in the "World Happiness Report" conducted by the same organization, our country unfortunately ranked 98th (<https://www.bbc.com/turkce/articles>). In today's circumstances, factors such as global and national economic crises, natural disasters, pandemics, technological developments, and the accelerating pace of life adversely affect individuals, influencing their emotions and behaviors. Consequently, the importance of emotion management—one of the key components of positive psychology—becomes increasingly apparent for both employees and workplaces. In this context, the present study aims to raise awareness among courthouse employees, who experience higher workloads, work-related stress, and physical and psychological exhaustion compared to other institutions due to their direct interaction with the public, in both their professional and private lives. Furthermore, the study seeks to serve as a starting point for future theoretical research and draw attention to the importance of emotion management and work-life balance for employees in a practical sense.

Methodology

This section will address the results of the study, which examines the impact of emotion management—an area within the increasingly popular field of positive psychology—on job satisfaction and work-life balance. Emotion management is an area that requires more research in Turkey. The study's primary population consists of employees working at the Ankara Courthouse. As of 2024, approximately 3,350 individuals are employed at this institution. Data was collected using a non-random sampling method, specifically convenience sampling, resulting in a total of 418 participants.

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The data obtained through questionnaire forms were processed using SPSS 26.0 software. For demographic variables such as gender, age, number of children, marital status, education level, years of service, and job title, parametric tests were employed. Specifically, the T-test was used for comparisons between two groups, while one-way ANOVA tests were applied for comparisons involving more than two groups. Additionally, the reliability of the scales was assessed using the widely accepted Cronbach's Alpha analysis.

Findings

For the demographic variables including gender, age, number of children, marital status, educational background, years of employment, and job title, parametric tests were employed in the analyses. Specifically, T-tests were used for comparisons between two groups, and ANOVA tests were applied for comparisons involving more than two groups.

Figure 1: Descriptive Statistics for Research Scales

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Participants scored an average of 85.07 on the Emotion Management Scale. Among the sub-dimensions, the highest scores were obtained from the emotional awareness sub-dimension, while the lowest scores were from the cognitive appraisal sub-dimension. The scale and all its sub-dimensions met the assumption of normality. The Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient calculated for this study is $\alpha = 0.944$. For the emotional awareness sub-dimension, this value is 0.939; for the cognitive appraisal sub-dimension, it is 0.841; and for reflection, it is 0.931.

Figure 2: Comparison of participants' scores from the emotional management scale with gender (T-Test)

To determine whether the scores obtained by participants on the emotion management scale differ by gender, T-tests were conducted. The results reveal a statistically significant difference in the emotional awareness subscale ($p < 0.05$). **The significant differences are attributed to the higher average scores obtained by female participants in this subscale.** This can be interpreted as indicating that the detailed characteristics and work styles of female employees contribute positively to the emotional awareness dimension.

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Figure 3: Comparison of participants' scores from the emotional management scale with marital status (T-Test)

According to the T-tests conducted to determine whether the scores participants received on the Emotional Orientation Scale varied by marital status; no statistically significant differences were found ($p > 0.05$).

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Figure 4: Comparison of the participants' scores from the emotional management scale with their educational status (ANOVA)

According to the results of the ANOVA conducted to determine whether participants' scores on the emotional orientation scale differed based on their educational background, statistically significant differences were found in both the scale as a whole and the emotional awareness sub-dimension ($p < 0.05$). Post-Hoc analyses, specifically Tukey's test, revealed significant differences among the high school, associate degree, and bachelor's degree options. ***The significant differences observed are attributed to the higher average scores obtained by participants with an associate degree.***

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Figure 5: Comparison of participants' scores from the emotion orientation scale with age (ANOVA)

As shown in Figure 5, there are no statistically significant differences based on age ($p > 0.05$). The research results indicate a statistically significant and positive relationship between emotion management and work-life balance. It was concluded that as the scores for emotion management increase, the scores for work-life balance also increase.

Additionally, descriptive results from the emotion management scale, based on the research data, reveal that cognitive evaluation scores are lower compared to other dimensions (Figure 1). In terms of gender, female employees have higher scores in the emotional awareness sub-dimension of emotion management (Figure 2). Regarding education level, master's degree holders have higher averages in the reflection dimension, while bachelor's degree holders positively influence the average in the cognitive evaluation and emotional awareness dimensions (Figure 4). When considering the age of employees, the data show that the overall average is higher for those aged 50 and above, and the scores for emotional awareness are notably higher in the 40-49 age range compared to other age groups (Figure 5). These findings are among the notable results of the study.

Results

In the rapidly changing dynamics of contemporary work environments, it is important to reiterate the significance of emotion management for individuals, as it affects both their professional and personal lives. As Goleman points out, “Emotional literacy is as important for learning as mathematics and education,” and he introduced a four-stage model called SOCS (Situation, Options, Consequences, and Solutions) to address this issue. Based on his research, the outcomes of emotion management include:

- Greater resilience to feelings of frustration and helplessness and improved anger control,
- Reduction in behaviors such as verbal humiliation, fighting, and class disruptions,
- Expression of anger in an appropriate manner without engaging in physical altercations,
- Decrease in the penalties received for undesirable behaviors,
- Reduction in aggressive or self-harming behaviors,
- Development of more positive feelings about oneself and one’s family,
- Improved stress management,
- Lower levels of loneliness and social anxiety (Goleman, 2019).

It is important to emphasize that the SOCS courses provided to students have yielded positive results not only in emotion management but also in emotional self-awareness, effective use of emotions, empathy, and relationship management. As previously mentioned, the concept of emotion management is crucial for both professional and personal life, as it lays the foundation for positive outcomes and contributes to job performance and work-life balance. Therefore, I believe it is a concept that should be emphasized not only for students but also for working individuals. The significant and positive relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction highlights the need to address emotion management from both the employee's

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and employer's perspectives. In this regard, it would be beneficial to refer to the strategies outlined by Steele (1977) in his work to make the workplace suitable for all types of employees.

- **Optimistic Leadership:** Mentors or supervisors affirm the capabilities of employees.
- **Real Challenges:** Tasks that stretch an individual's abilities indicate respect for their potential and help them feel they are not confined by limiting patterns. These challenges are adjusted according to the person's skills, fostering a sense of achievable success.
- **Focus on Learning:** Emphasis is placed on the notion that expertise and competence develop over time through on-the-job learning and that proficiency increases with experience. This perspective challenges the erroneous belief that an individual's inherent capacity is limited by their affiliation with a specific group.
- **Affirmation of a Sense of Belonging:** Negative stereotypes can lead to feelings of not belonging and reinforce the belief that one's work is unsuitable. Therefore, supporting an individual's sense of belonging and aligning the assigned tasks with their actual skills is beneficial.
- **Valuing Multiple Perspectives:** Demonstrating appreciation for diverse viewpoints is crucial to prevent stereotypes and marginalization in the workplace.
- **Role Models:** Employees who view successful colleagues as role models can enhance their own success.
- **Building Confidence through Dialogic Feedback:** Constructive and appropriately given feedback should focus on guiding the individual positively rather than merely highlighting successes or failures. This approach not only fosters confidence but also minimizes the emotional cost of failure. (Goleman, 2007)

Although general recommendations based on previous studies have been mentioned above, in this section, I would like to address the issue specifically with regard to courthouse employees. Due to the nature of their work, courthouse employees spend long periods sitting in front of a computer, which leads to negative physiological consequences. In addition to this, it should not be overlooked that, compared to employees in other institutions, courthouse employees are also negatively affected psychologically by the content of the work they

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perform. Furthermore, the heavy workload, inadequate physical conditions, and the need for constant communication with both the public and their superiors highlight emotional management as an important concept that must be addressed for employees.

Therefore, emotional management will undoubtedly have a positive effect not only on employees but also on management within the institutional climate. From the perspective of employees, letting go of prejudices toward their work and management, not forgetting others while focusing on themselves, adopting a team spirit, loving the work they do even if it is not the work they ideally want to do, taking a more active role by generating new ideas related to their job, being aware of and recognizing their own emotions while also understanding the emotional state of others, maintaining open, effective, and positive communication, providing and receiving timely and constructive feedback will undoubtedly contribute positively to both their professional and personal lives.

From the management perspective, providing timely and constructive feedback, supporting social activities, and seeking input from employees on workflow matters are important as they foster a sense of belonging among employees. Another significant aspect is the provision of in-house training for managers and employees on topics such as emotional management, personal development, and psychological support by experts in the field, to ensure positive development in areas such as emotional management and emotional competence. It would also be beneficial to repeat such training at regular intervals for sustainability.

In conclusion, based on the participants in this study, I believe that, particularly in today's challenging conditions, it is crucial for all employees and management to increase their awareness of emotional management and subsequently improve it. Numerous studies have demonstrated the positive effects of emotional management not only in professional but also in personal life, and I believe that it should receive greater attention in both academic literature and practical applications.

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